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Maryana Kachynska –

Ph.D, associate professor

*police activity and public administration department of
Kharkiv National University of Internal Affairs
(27 Lva Landau Av., Kharkiv, 61080, Ukraine)*

Police Response to Cases of Cruelty to Animals that Contain Signs of an Administrative Offense: the Experience of Ukraine

Стаття присвячена питанню реагування поліцейськими на випадки жорстокого поводження із тваринами, що містять ознаки адміністративного правопорушення: досвід України. У статті автор вибудував алгоритм реагування поліцейськими в означеній категорії справ. Науковець деталізує застосування заходів забезпечення провадження у дані категорії справ. Звернута окрема увага на тому, що поліцейський вирішує питання про місце перебування тварини на час провадження у справі, наприклад, у випадку залишення тварини на призволяще.

Ключові слова: жорстоке поводження з тваринами, реагування поліцейськими на випадки жорстокого поводження з тваринами, вилучення тварини, правовий статус тварини, адміністративне провадження, стадії провадження.

Статья посвящена вопросу реагирования полицейскими на случаи жестокого обращения с животными, содержащие признаки административного правонарушения: опыт Украины. В статье автор выстроил алгоритм реагирования полицейскими в указанной категории дел. Автор детализирует применение мер обеспечения производства по данной категории дел. Обращено особое внимание на том, что полицейский решает вопрос о месте пребывания животного на время производства по делу, например, в случае оставления животного на произвол.

Ключевые слова: жестокое обращение с животными, реагирование полицейскими на случаи жестокого обращения с животными, изъятие животного, правовой статус животного, административное производство, стадии производства.

The article is devoted to the issue of police responses to animal cruelty cases that contain signs of an administrative offense: the experience of Ukraine.

In the article the author developed a step-by-step response for police officers in case of offenses under Article 89 of the Code of Ukraine on Administrative Offenses. The powers of the National Police of Ukraine in this category of cases were also analyzed step by step.

The administrative and jurisdictional powers of police officers during proceedings on the fact of animal cruelty are considered. The author details the application of measures to ensure the proceedings in these categories of cases. The article pays special attention to the fact that the police officer decides on the whereabouts of the animal at the time of the proceedings, for example, in the case of leaving the animal in a temporary home. The author also gives practical examples of the interaction between animal protection organizations and the police during the seizure of the animal before considering the case on its merits. The telephone number of the all-Ukrainian hotline for assistance to animals is given, namely 0-800-302-303. An analysis is given of the legal status of the animal in accordance with current Ukrainian legislation.

The article separately analyzes the stages of proceedings on animal cruelty. The powers of the National Police and the court to consider this category of cases have been clarified, and their limitations have been clarified.

Article 283 of UCAO determines the content of the resolution. It must contain: the name of the body that made the decision, the official who issued the decision, the date of the case; information about the person in respect of whom the case is being considered; statement of the circumstances established during the consideration of the case; indication of Article 89 of the Code of Administrative Offenses, which provides for liability for this administrative offense; the

decision made in the case. According to the content of the decision, the decision may be a) on the imposition of an administrative penalty; b) on closing the case.

Thus, according to the current legislation, the police have a set of jurisdictional powers to prevent, detect, stop and prosecute perpetrators of animal cruelty.

Keywords: animal cruelty, police response to animal cruelty, seizure of animals, legal status of animals, administrative proceedings, stages of proceedings, consideration of the administrative case, seizure of the animal for consideration on the merits, evidence of cruelty to animals.

Addressing the problem. New challenges of the reform process in Ukraine require improvement of the standards of police response to offenses in general and in the field of animal protection in particular.

Analysis of research and publications. The issue of police response to various types of offenses has been the subject of research by many scientists, namely: I. Andrusevich, A. Bayvel, D. Zhuravlyov, N. Zubchenko, O. Spectrum, M. Mikievich, C. Khimchenko and others. Peculiarities of police response to cases of animal cruelty that contain signs of administrative offenses have been studied in the works of such national scientists as V. Alexandrenko, V. Veresha, S. Denisov, O. Shumilo, S. Yakushev and others.

Previously unsolved problems. However, taking into account the incomplete process of improving current Ukrainian legislation in the field of animal welfare, improving legal liability for cruelty to animals, reforming the National Police of Ukraine, the difference in the effectiveness of police response to cases of animal cruelty, some aspects need them further research. This determines the relevance of the study of police responses to animal cruelty cases that contain signs of an administrative offense: the experience of Ukraine.

Basic content. Today, attention has significantly increased to the problem of preventing animal cruelty in Ukraine and around the world [1, p.23]. That is why we will consider systematic actions of the police during consideration of statements and reports on the commission of cruel treatment containing signs of an administrative offense (item 89 of **Ukrainian Code of Administrative Offenses** (further UCAO)):

- takes all measures for the immediate cessation of animal cruelty;
- if necessary, provides veterinary help to the animal;
- reports the animal rescue hotline by phone 0 800 302 303;

- accepts report (if it did not exist) orally or in writing from the complainant (if any), which is entered in the Universal Data Base [2];

- explains to the complainant the procedure for consideration of his / her appeal, constitutional rights and obligations (in particular, the right not to testify against himself and his relatives; the right to defense; each person is presumed innocent until the court finds otherwise, and others [3]), as well as warns under the signature of criminal liability for knowingly false notification of a crime under Art. 383 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine [4];

- draws up a report on an administrative offense under Art. 89 "Animal Cruelty" of Ukrainian Code of Administrative Offenses;

- if necessary, apply measures to ensure proceedings in cases of administrative offenses. That is, in order to stop the offense, when other measures of influence are exhausted (Article 260 of the Ukrainian Code of Administrative Offenses), police officers, including a district police officer, patrol police officer, are entitled to administrative detention of the offender (paragraph 1 of Article 262 of The Ukrainian Code of Administrative Offenses)[5]. Namely, administrative detention is carried out by police in violation of the rules of hunting, fishing and protection of fish stocks and other violations of legislation on the protection and use of wildlife. In cases directly provided by the laws of Ukraine, in order to terminate administrative offenses, when other measures of influence, identification, drawing up a report on an administrative offense in case of impossibility to draw it up at the scene of the offense, if drawing up a report is mandatory, ensuring timely and correct consideration of cases and execution of decisions on cases of administrative offenses, administrative detention of a person is allowed. A report on administrative detention must be drawn up in accordance with the provisions of the current legislation. It should be remembered that paragraph 3 of Article 264 of The Ukrainian Code of Administrative Offenses states that when violating the legislation on the protection and use of

wildlife, including animal cruelty, police officers may also conduct a personal search and inspection of items. A personal examination of an offender may be conducted by a police officer of the same sex as the person being examined and in the presence of two witnesses of the same sex. When committing violations of the legislation on the protection and use of wildlife, in addition to authorized officials of the bodies exercising state supervision over the observance of hunting rules, fishery protection bodies, police officers may inspect vehicles in the prescribed manner [5].

Inspection of things, hand luggage, luggage, fishing and fishing gear, harvested products, vehicles and other items is carried out, as a rule, in the presence of the person in whose ownership (possession) they are. In urgent cases, these items may be inspected with the participation of two witnesses in the absence of the owner. A report shall be drawn up on the personal inspection of items, or a corresponding entry shall be made in the report on an administrative offense or in the report on administrative detention.

– **The police officer decides on the whereabouts of the animal at the time of the proceedings.** For example, in a case where the animal was abandoned, it can be rehoused by the person who found it. Also, you need to be aware that, according to Article 341 of the Civil Code of Ukraine, that the person who found and looked after (rehoused) the abandoned animal can become the animal's owner if:

- a) nobody claims ownership of cattle for 6 months;
- b) all other animals for 2 months [6].

In accordance with *paragraph 1 of Article 180 of the Civil Code of Ukraine*, animals have the legal status of things and they are a special object of civil rights. Therefore, a *police officer may seize an animal until the case is decided*, in accordance with Article 265 Seizure of things and documents of Ukrainian Code of Administrative Offenses. A report shall be drawn up on the seizure of the animal, or a corresponding entry shall be made in the report on an administrative offense, on inspection of items or administrative detention.

The location of the animal can be established directly with the representatives of *animal protection organizations* (notifying of such a need by phone 0-800-302-303), and issued by the **Act of transfer for safekeeping**, according to which the animal protector who takes the animal is obliged to take care of animal, to provide it with appropriate

conditions for living, treatment, nutrition and satisfaction of its natural needs in accordance with the species of animal and the state of its health.

– **the police officer builds an administrative case on the fact of animal cruelty.** The district police officer collects the necessary information to make a decision, for example:

- a) interviews witnesses;
- b) finds out the circumstances of animal cruelty;
- c) the presence of mitigating or aggravating circumstances;
- d) collects evidence in the case;
- e) involves specialists who provide information. For example, in the case of animal cruelty, beatings or other acts of violence that caused the animal physical pain, suffering and did not cause bodily harm, injury or death, the commission of such actions with the animal;
- f) information characterizing the offender from the place of work, study, residence;
- g) carries out registration of the offender for The Prevention Register;
- e) establishes the presence or absence of administrative or criminal liability for cruelty to animals;
- h) other information relevant to the qualification and decision-making on the merits. For example, committing the offense in the presence of a child, cruel treatment of an animal to satisfy sexual desire, cruel treatment of 2 or more animals, committed by a group of persons, etc .;

– **consideration of an administrative case of cruel treatment and decision-making in the case of animals is attributed to the powers of the National Police** (Article 222 of Ukrainian Code of Administrative Offenses) **and the court** (Article 221 of Ukrainian Code of Administrative Offenses);

It should be remembered that in accordance with Article 29, Article 32, Article 89 of the Ukrainian Code of Administrative Offenses for cruelty to animals, only the court may order administrative arrest and confiscation of the animal, if the animal's owner is a threat to his life or health. In accordance with Article 27, Article 89, the National Police for animal cruelty may impose an administrative penalty in the form of a fine [5].

In case of cruel treatment of animals (Article 89 of The Ukrainian Code of Administrative Offenses) by a person aged 16 to 17, the consideration of such a case is only within the competence of the court,

a police officer in any case can not consider such a case.

Consideration of an administrative case of this category includes three stages: 1) *preparation of the case for consideration*; 2) *consideration of the case*; 3) *decision-making (resolution)*.

There are a number of mandatory rules for dealing with a case. According to Art. 278 of The Ukrainian Code of Administrative Offenses, the body (official), namely the police (judge), in preparation for the case of an administrative offense under Article 89 of The Ukrainian Code of Administrative Offenses decides the following issues: whether it is within its competence to consider the case; whether the protocol and other materials of the case on an administrative offense have been drawn up correctly; whether the persons participating in the consideration of the case have been notified of the time and place of its consideration; whether additional materials are needed; whether the petitions of the person prosecuted, the victim, their legal representatives and the lawyer are subject to satisfaction.

The term of consideration of the administrative case on cruel treatment of animals in accordance with Part 1 of Art. 277 UCAO makes 15 days and according to Art. 276 UCAO cases are considered on a place of commission of an offense.

After the preparatory stage, the hearing begins. The relevant procedure is defined in Art. 279 of Ukrainian Code of Administrative Offenses. Consideration begins with the presentation of an official (police officer, judge) who decides the case. This is followed by the announcement of the case under consideration and who is being held administratively liable [5]. All rights and responsibilities are explained to all participants in the proceedings. Then the protocol on the administrative offense provided by Art. 89 UCAO is declared. Article 280 of UCAO defines the list of circumstances to be clarified during the consideration of the case. This is the responsibility of the official who has the authority to hear the case (police officer, judge). The following information is to be clarified whether: animal cruelty was committed, as provided for in Article 89 of UCAO; the person is guilty of committing it; it is subject to administrative or other liability; there are mitigating and aggravating circumstances; property damage was caused; other circumstances relevant to the proper resolution of the case [5].

Article 280 of UCAO defines the list of circumstances to be clarified during the consideration of the case. This is the responsibility of the official who has the authority to hear the case (police officer, judge). The following information is to be clarified whether: animal cruelty was committed, as provided for in Article 89 UCAO; the person is guilty of committing it; it is subject to administrative or other liability; there are mitigating and aggravating circumstances; property damage was caused; other circumstances relevant to the proper resolution of the case [5].

Evidence in an administrative case of animal cruelty is any factual data on the basis of which the police officer (judge) clarifies these circumstances in the manner prescribed by law. These data are included in the protocol on administrative offenses: explanations of the person prosecuted, victims, witnesses, expert opinions, physical evidence, testimony of technical devices used during the supervision of traffic rules. A separate report on the seizure of items and documents, as well as other documents (for example, inspection reports, various certificates, characteristics, a report on administrative detention, personal inspection or inspection of items, etc.). The police officer evaluates the evidence (i.e. decides on its reliability) according to his inner conviction, which is based on a comprehensive, complete and objective investigation of all the circumstances of the case together, guided by law and legal awareness (Articles 251-252 of UCAO).

Consideration of the case of commission ends with the adoption of a resolution in the case of an administrative offense (Chapter 23 of UCAO).

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